

A Study of the Chloro Complexes of Cobalt(II) using Liquid Anion-exchange and Spectrophotometry*

K. S. Venkateswarlu and Manohar Lal

Using tri-*n*-nonylamine in benzene as the extractant for cobalt(II) from HCl solutions, the increase in the percentage extraction has been found up to 8*M*-HCl; it decreases with further increase in HCl molarity. At 3.5, 6, 8.5, and 11*M*-HCl, the distribution coefficient has been determined, taking different percentages of the amine in the diluent. The experimental data have been analysed by plotting $\log D$ against $\alpha \pm_{HCl}$ or $\log \% \text{amine}$. From this it is concluded that the ion pair in the solvent phase may be $[\text{RNH}]_2^+ [\text{CoCl}_4]^{2-}$. The result has been confirmed by spectrophotometric method.

Good and Bryan¹ extracted Co(II) from hydrochloric acid solutions into tri-*n*-hexylamine in benzene. Good and Holland² did the same from LiCl solutions. These authors did not analyse their data on the basis of the treatment developed by Irving and Rossette³. They presented, however, other evidences to indicate the species extracted as $[\text{CoCl}_4]^{2-}$. The difference in behaviour noticed in the above work, when the aqueous medium is altered, indicates that there may be more than one species being extracted. A detailed investigation on the chloro-complexes of cobalt(II), using the technique of liquid anion-exchange with tri-*n*-nonylamine (TNA) and spectrophotometry, is presented in this communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the reagents employed were of A.R. quality. Tri-*n*-nonylamine was purified several times before use. In solvent extraction experiments Co-60 was employed as the tracer and the measurement of the activity in both the organic liquid and aqueous phases was carried out on a scintillation crystal assembly. The distribution coefficient was calculated from these data. In all the experiments the solvent phase (TNA in benzene) was pre-equilibrated with the appropriate aqueous phase.

DISCUSSION

Variation of Hydrochloric Acid Molarity.—Several experiments were carried out at different molarities of HCl, ranging from 2.5 to 10.7 (*ca.*). The results are recorded in Table I.

*Read at the First Annual Convention of Chemists, held under the auspices of the Indian Chemical Society in Bombay in December, 1963.

1. *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1961, 20, 140.
2. *Ibid.*, 1962, 24, 1683.
3. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 1908.

TABLE I

Molarity of HCl.	% Extraction.	Distribution coeff. (D).	Molarity of HCl.	% Extraction.	Distribution coeff. (D).
2.4	1.50	0.015	5.30	71.4	2.50
3.0	4.70	0.049	5.60	80.0	4.27
3.3	6.53	0.070	6.35	93.3	14.00
4.1	22.10	0.280	7.70	95.6	22.00
4.7	40.70	0.690	9.30	90.8	9.87
			10.74	66.7	2.01

The data clearly indicate that the distribution coefficient increases up to 9M and decreases with further increase in HCl molarity. This behaviour is similar to that observed by Good and Bryan¹ and by Moore and Kraus⁵ in their anion-exchange studies. The usual interpretation of this phenomenon is that the decrease in the distribution coefficients is

due to the increasing competition of the free chloride ions for the exchangeable sites. In LiCl medium, Good and Holland² did not observe this behaviour. A general explanation, as suggested by Moore⁵, is that the liquid anion-exchangers preferentially extract uni-negative species. The plots of $\log D$ against $\log a_{\pm \text{HCl}}$ for the data in Table I are shown in Fig. 1. Also plotted in this figure are the analysed data of Good and Bryan¹ for *n*-hexylamine-HCl system and the data of Good and Holland² for *n*-hexylamine-LiCl system. For the HCl solutions, the slopes of the plots are about the same, viz., 3, whereas for LiCl solutions, the slope is 2. On this basis the species that are likely to be extracted are CoCl_4^- , HCoCl_4^- and CoCl_4^{2-} .

FIG. 1

(% amine) vs. $\log D$ plot is shown in Fig. 2.

The data in Table II were analysed by plotting $\log D$ against $\log$ (% amine) for each molarity of the acid. At 3.5, 6, and 8.5M hydrochloric acid, these straight line plots provided a slope of 1.5. The fractional slope can only be explained on the basis that at least two species are extracted, one of which being uni-negative. At 11.0M-HCl, slope of the log-log plot, however, is of the order of 2, possibly due to the extraction of CoCl_4^{2-} alone. Taking

1. J. Amer. Chem. Soc., 1952, 74, 843.

5. Moore, NAS-NS, 3101.

Variation of the Amine Concentration.—

In order to distinguish the complexes, the charge on the extracted species was determined at different molarities of HCl by varying the percentage of amine at each molarity. The results are recorded in Table II and a typical log

these results into account, one can explain the slope value of those obtained in the earlier experiments by the following conversion:

TABLE II

%TNA in benzene.	Distribution coefficient in			Molarity of HCl=11.0.	
	3.5M-HCl.	6.0M-HCl.	8.5M-HCl.	% TNA in benzene.	Distribution coeff. (D).
0.5	..	..	0.76	0.1	0.004
1.0	0.003	0.19	2.03	0.2	0.015
1.5	..	..	3.70	0.3	0.031
2.0	0.009	0.52	5.30	0.4	0.0620
2.5	0.013	0.74	7.48	..	..
3.0	0.017	1.10	9.00	0.6	0.100
4.0	0.029	1.40	13.30	..	..
4.5	0.035	1.70	..	0.8	0.180
5.0	0.037	1.95	17.20	..	..
5.5	0.044	2.29	..	1.0	0.250
6.0	0.052	2.48	..	..	..
7.0	0.062	3.00	..	..	..

As stated earlier, we have analysed the data in lithium chloride medium obtained by

Good and Hilland². In this case a slope of the order of 2 was obtained, indicating the conversion of CoCl_2 to CoCl_4^{2-} . Incidentally, the data obtained in lithium chloride medium do not fully support those available with HCl.

FIG. 2

Spectrophotometric Studies

The intensity of the blue colour, exhibited by cobaltous solutions, has been observed to increase with the increasing concentration of Cl^- ions. The complex is generally believed to be CoCl_4^{2-} . Katzin⁶ has observed that Co(II) solutions in presence of excess of Cl^- ions in acetone medium exhibit absorption at $695 \text{ m}\mu$ with shoulders at $625 \text{ m}\mu$ and $665 \text{ m}\mu$. Similar results were also reported by Good and Bryan¹. The present authors have studied the growth of the $695 \text{ m}\mu$ band with increasing hydrochloric acid, using a Beckman spectrophotometer. Assuming that all cobaltous species exist as CoCl_4^{2-} (protonated or otherwise) in 12 molar HCl, its extinction coefficient has been

determined to be 565. From the optical densities at 695 m μ observed for all the other solutions, the %cobalt in the form of CoCl_4^{2-} has been evaluated. From this the ratio,

$$R = [\text{CoCl}_4^{2-}] / [\text{CoCl}_x]^{(2-x)}$$

was computed. A plot of $\log R$ vs. $\log a_{\pm \text{HCl}}$ provides a straight line (Fig. 3) with a slope

FIG. 3

of 3. The results can only be explained by assuming the conversion of CoCl^+ to CoCl_4^{2-} . This is the first time that such an analysis has been applied to spectrophotometric data. The above studies lead to two conclusions:

(a) Concentration of CoCl_4^{2-} apparently increases with increasing chloride ion concentration.

(b) In the same region of chloride concentrations (8-12M HCl), the extraction of cobalt into the anion exchanger decreases.

These can be explained if one assumes that CoCl_4^{2-} is being converted to HCoCl_4^- , extractability of which may be poor. The spectral evidence of this conversion will have to be looked for in UV and IR regions.

The authors are grateful to Dr. J. Shankar for his keen interest and to Shri P. N. Moorthy for his help in preliminary experiments.